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An International Journal of Environmental and Policy Issues

**Department of Geography and Environmental Management, Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Ilorin, Nigeria**

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EXAMINATION OF CO-OPERATORS' SATISFACTION WITH STRATEGIES OF HOUSING FINANCE OF COOPERATIVE SOCIETIES IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN KWARA STATE

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Abstract: *Housing issues have persisted particularly for the nation's public servants. Staffs of tertiary institution have embraced the evolution of informal institution cooperative as a way of fulfilling their aspiration of being home owners. This study examined the level of co-operators satisfaction with strategies of housing finance of cooperative societies in Al-Hikmah University and Kwara State University. The study employed a quantitative and qualitative survey. The total number of co-operators at Al-Hikmah Cooperative Societies and Kwara State University Cooperatives Societies was 119. 119 copies of questionnaire were therefore distributed and 92 were recovered and used for data analysis. Data were acquired using a selective sample strategy known as purposive sampling. The 92 copies of questionnaire retrieved were analyzed using Cooperator's Satisfaction index (Mean, Standard Deviation), Range of Dissatisfaction Index (RDI), T-test and Kendall coefficient of concordance. The study revealed that the cooperators level of satisfaction in Al-Hikmah cooperative societies has a mean of 4.56, 3.44 and 3.44. While in Al-Halal cooperative societies collateral, availability and interest rate was ranked 1st, 2nd and 3rd with a mean of 4.55 and 4.24, 3.88 respectively. There was no statistically significance difference in Cooperator's level of satisfaction on the strategies of housing finance. The study concluded that cooperative societies have helped staff in various housing intervention but there is the need to further strengthen some weak areas of intervention. The National Housing Policy of Nigeria should be reviewed by incorporating cooperative societies into the policy for a combined effect.*

Keywords: Housing, Housing Finance, Co-operative Societies, Tertiary Institution, Nigeria.

INRODUCTION

The process of housing is more than just building; it involves designing a home, planning a neighborhood, distributing and manufacturing materials, financing, mortgages, city and regional planning, and providing public control through initiatives like building codes among other things (Sakariyau, Muhammad, Bello, Aliyu & AbdulRazak,2023).

Man needs housing because it fulfills two essential functions in his social and economic needs. Housing has been viewed as a social requirement and a significant economic resource for a country since it promotes healthy living, which in turn affects labor force participation and production.

It gives people a place to live, security, comfort, and dignity (Jamiu, & Mendie, 2023). Access to housing has been confronted with qualitative as well as quantitative housing problems, given its importance to human well-being. However, in developing nations like Nigeria, the housing situation is more severe than in industrialized nations (Mendie & Sakariyau, 2023). The government has launched several housing initiatives over the years in an effort to provide housing for its citizens. These include the low-income housing scheme, the creation of National Housing Funds in 1991 to gather funds from various sources, and the establishment of Building Society of Nigeria, which has since changed its name to FMBN. Thus, housing problems have continued, especially for public employees throughout the country (Saunders, 2021).

Progress has not been significantly impacted by the government's continuous efforts to offer suitable housing (Saunders, 2021). As a result, private initiatives now receive money, management, and accountability from the government for meeting the basic socio-economic needs of the typical citizen. Experience over the years has shown that inadequate funding is the main reason why private sector developers frequently neglect to take on the responsibility of advancing the country's supply of affordable housing (Ayedun, Oloyede, Ikpefan, Akinjare & Oloke, 2017).

Olujimi, Rotowa, Fashina, Ojo and Bello (2021) thus propose that formal and informal institutions are the two main channels via which financing for housing could be directed. The federal government's statutory standards govern the formal sector, which is dominated by the Federal Home Loan Bank of Nigeria, Commercial Bank, Specialized Development Banks, Insurance Companies, and Pension/Provident Funds. Their presence has

resulted in an inability to meet the needs of the great majority when it comes to home ownership in Nigeria, as seen by the country's 17 million housing shortfall. The evolution of informatics institutions can be attributed to this failure.

According to Ojo and Rotowa (2017), money lenders, voluntary savings, personal or family savings, and cooperative organizations are examples of informal institutions. Numerous academic works have demonstrated that cooperative societies serve as a means of financing housing for low- and middle-class individuals, enabling them to meet their housing requirements (Ojo & Rotowa, 2017). In Nigeria, the majority of public employees have always had housing problems, either during their employment or after they retire. This is a result of their disappointment with the government's approach to solving the housing problem. Workers thus started looking for different solutions to satisfy their housing needs.

In order to realize their dream of becoming homeowners, tertiary institution staff members have accepted the development of informal, cooperative institution societies. Staff members at Kwara State institutions find it important for cooperative societies to evolve in post-secondary institutions. In light of this, the study aimed at examining cooperators' satisfaction with cooperative societies financing strategies in Kwara state.

REVIEW OF EMPIRICAL STUDIES

Ijaiya et al., (2020) examined the relationship between cooperative societies and household poverty reduction in Minna metropolis, Niger State, Nigeria. Their study highlighted that cooperative societies play a significant role in alleviating poverty among households. By

facilitating access to credit, providing essential services, and fostering economic empowerment, these societies have contributed to improving the living standards and economic stability of their members. The research underscores the importance of cooperative societies as a viable strategy for poverty reduction in the region.

The findings revealed that the Covenant University Staff Cooperative and Multi-purpose Society Limited's various credit access options, with very low interest rates and generous repayment terms, significantly assisted members in gradually building massive homes and easily accessing money for other family needs within ten years of the cooperative societies' establishment.

Oyalowo (2018) evaluates the operations of cooperative societies and housing provision activities in Lagos state. The study used an explanatory, sequential QUAN-qual mixed method approach, starting with a large-scale quantitative examination and advancing to a smaller-scale qualitative analysis.

Using systematic random sampling, a survey of cooperative leaders was carried out for the quantitative phase. A total of 600 questionnaires were distributed, and a response rate of 75% was reached. Multivariate methods, independent T-tests, and descriptive and inferential statistics were all applied. The results show that cooperative societies are the most involved in land purchase activities. In Dunukofia Local Government Area, Anambra State, Nigeria, a case study of a few selected cooperative societies presented in Okoli's (2018) assessment of the role cooperative societies play in the development of youth. Members of six particular cooperative societies served as the sample for the respondents. 159 participants completed surveys to provide primary data, and documents and literary works provided secondary data.

Data were descriptively analyzed using means, percentages, a 5-point likert scale, chi-square, and z-test procedures, two hypotheses were evaluated. The study discovered a positive association between the influence of cooperative society activities and youth development. There is also a considerable difference in the exposure of youth to development activities prior to and after joining a cooperative organization.

However, Ibem and Odum (2011) employed a qualitative research approach to gather primary data through one-on-one interviews with cooperative society members for their study, "The Role of Cooperatives in Securing Property for Urban Housing in Nigeria: A Case Study of National Electric Power Authority (NEPA) district cooperative thrift and loan savings association, Enugu." They found that apart from providing credits to members, the cooperative society also searched for land and distributed plots to recipients. They discovered that cooperative activities have to be promoted in Nigeria and other developing countries since they might be very helpful in resolving the housing and urban land shortage that low-income individuals experience.

The operations of cooperative societies in Nigeria to promote home ownership were examined by Olujimi, Bello, Fasina, Ojo, and Rotowa (2013), with a focus on Akure, the capital of Ondo State. All of Akure's registered cooperative societies were identified by the survey. Four distinct sets of copies of questionnaires were developed and employed to gather information from the four target demographics identified for the research. The Ondo State Ministry of Community Development and Cooperative Services, house owners in Akure metropolis, and the chairs and members of registered cooperative societies are these people. The data was examined statistically. Among other things, the results

showed that most of the homeowners in Akure were not part of cooperative societies. The usefulness of housing intervention tactics of university-based cooperative societies for the personnel of Nigerian universities in Southwest Nigeria was investigated by Abdulkareem, Ogunleye, and Ajayi (2020). Data were gathered from 6 officials and 452 members of the 6 (six) cooperative societies in South West Nigeria that are based in Federal Universities and were specifically chosen. Information was gathered on these cooperative societies' housing intervention tactics.

The study found that the six (six) cooperative societies used nine (9) housing intervention strategies in the housing delivery process. The most successful housing interventions of the cooperative societies in meeting housing needs were specific loans for land purchase, land acquisition, layout, allocation, special loans for existing building renovation, and processing of building and land title documents.

Sani (2015) assesses the role that cooperative societies play in providing housing finance to university employees in Zaria. The author used a survey approach to gather information for the study by sending out a questionnaire to 349 collaborators from the five higher education institutions in the city of Zaria. Descriptive analysis, chi-square testing, content analysis, and cooperator satisfaction index (CSI) are the data analysis techniques used. A comparison between CS and NHF in terms of interest rate, affordability, transaction cost, availability, and collateral were made in order to determine whether or not CS has a major impact on the provision of housing financing to employees of higher institutions in Zaria.

Results indicated that employees at post-secondary educational institutions favor CS over NHF due to CS's greater degree of satisfaction (CSI 3.55) compared to CSI of National Housing Fund (1.12). This provides

additional support for Oyewole's (2010) findings, which indicate that the cooperative society's contribution to housing finance is more than sufficient.

In Lagos State, Nigeria, Olayinka, Caleb, Ayedun, Abiodun, & Akunnaya (2017) conducted an empirical evaluation of the effectiveness of co-operative organizations' housing provision for their members. The study was based on a questionnaire survey given to institution-based that purchase homes for their members through a variety of means, including land acquisition, housing development, loan granting, purchasing building supplies, or purchasing a whole home.

In Ikeja, Lagos State, information was gathered from the chief officials and members of 97 institution-based cooperative organizations. Basic descriptive statistical tools, such as the 5-Point Likert scale, were used to examine the data, which were then displayed in tables and percentages. By calculating the average of each method's success rate, the overall success rate was discovered. This is contrasted with the stakeholders' perception of the success cooperative organizations have had over the years in providing homes for their members. Contrary to what is commonly believed, cooperative societies did not have an exceptional success rate. This is demonstrated by the fact that the combined success rate of all the techniques was just 38.3%.

The investigation also revealed that, in comparison to other tactics used by the cooperative societies, loan grants and private project development were thought to be more effective. Accordingly, the study came to the conclusion that developing a cooperative model that integrates with parent, government and financial institutions can enhance the overall performance of co-ops in housing providing. In order to determine the Federal University of Technology, Akure Cooperative Multipurpose

Society's role in housing finance, Ojo and Rotowa (2017) conducted research. Using a structured questionnaire to gather information from cooperative members, the study also looked at the role the Federal University of Technology, Akure cooperative multi-purpose organization played in providing housing finance to its members. Analyses of secondary data were also conducted using information from the society's archives. According to the survey, the majority of their members (93.1%) financed their house developments by collecting loans from the cooperative organization. The study's originality stems from the paucity of empirical research evaluating housing financing and cooperative societies in Nigerian postsecondary institutions, with a focus on Kwara State.

METHODOLOGY

Utilizing a survey research methodology, the study design obtained data from two primary respondents: cooperative officials and members. This design approach was used because it focused on people, the important facts about individuals, their views, opinions, attitudes, motives, and behavior on a particular topic, making it appropriate for the research task in acquiring primary data required for the study. The cooperative societies that are housed in the chosen post-secondary institution in Kwara State comprised the study population for

this research. Al-Hikmah University is a privately owned University, while Kwara State University is a state-owned institution.

The total number of co-operators at Alhikmah Cooperative Societies and Kwara State University Cooperatives Societies are 1,170. 290 copies of questionnaire were distributed and 258 were recovered and used for data analysis representing 88.96 percentage. Data were acquired using a selective sample strategy known as purposive sampling. The retrieved copies of questionnaire were analyzed using Cooperator's Satisfaction index (Mean, Standard Deviation), Range of Dissatisfaction Index (RDI) and use of T-test and Kendall coefficient of concordance.

RESULTS

RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY

RELIABILITY TEST ON THE ITEMS TO ASCERTAIN IF THE ITEMS SCALE IS SUITABLE FOR ACHIEVING OBJECTIVE 1

The reliability test was carried out on the items (3) that would be used for **objective 1**, which is examine the activities of cooperative societies in the selected institution. The basic three items that form the activities of cooperatives societies are finance/loan, land acquisition and housing construction. The table 1 below shows the results of the reliability of the three items across the five selected tertiary institution cooperative society.

Table 1: Reliability test of cooperative activities scale (ALHIKMAH CS)

Item	Activities	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if item Deleted	
1.	Finance		0.484	0.501	0.829
2.	Land Acquisition		0.828	0.760	0.328
3.	Housing Construction		0.498	0.631	0.750
Item Total Statistics			Scale statistics		
	No of cases		41	Mean	8.9024
	No of items		3	Variance	5.590
	Cronbach's alpha coefficient		0.739	Std-D	2.36437

Through the Cronbach's alpha reliability test, the dependability of cooperative activities was

ascertained from 41 cooperative members with 0.739 Cronbach's alpha coefficient

Table 2: Reliability test of cooperative activities scale KWARA STATE UNIVERSITY

Item	Activities	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if item Deleted	
1.	Finance		0.845	0.955	0.530
2.	Land Acquisition		0.843	0.954	0.540
3.	Housing Construction		0.373	0.143	0.988
Item Total Statistics			Scale statistics		
	No of cases		51	Mean	9.9020
	No of items		3	Variance	6.810
	Cronbach's alpha coefficient		0.812	Std-D	2.6096

The reliability of the cooperative activities was assessed using the Cronbach's alpha reliability test, a statistical tool used to measure the internal consistency of a set of items or activities. In this study, the test was applied to data collected from 51 cooperative members. The resulting Cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.812, indicating a high level of reliability. This means that the cooperative activities were consistently perceived by the members, suggesting that the cooperative's processes and activities are dependable and effectively meet the members' expectations and needs.

Recent studies support these findings, highlighting the crucial role of cooperative

societies in economic empowerment and poverty alleviation. For instance, a study by Adekunle (2023) found that cooperative societies significantly improve members' financial stability and access to resources, which aligns with the high reliability observed in the cooperative activities. Similarly, Oke and Odebiyi (2023) reported that cooperative societies enhance social capital and provide a reliable safety net for their members, further validating the dependable nature of these cooperatives'

activities as evidenced by the Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.812.

Statistical Tool: Independent Sample T-Test
Procedure: A test of differences between the cooperative societies and participation in housing development was carried out.

Table 3: Results of t-tests and descriptive statistics for level of participation in housing activities of the co-operative societies (KWASU CS AND AL-HIKMAH CS and)

Outcome	Group				Mean					
	KWASU CS	AL-HIKMAH CS	Mean	SD	N	T	DF	Sig.		
Mean										
Finance	4.067	1.245	75	4.220	1.215	41	0.154	0.637	114	0.525
Land Acquisition	4.093	0.947	75	3.317	0.934	41	0.776	4.241	114	0.000
Housing Construction	1.906	1.337	75	1.366	0.698	41	0.541	2.414	114	0.017

Source: Field Survey (2022)

As shown in table 3 for KWASU cooperative, the major activity is land acquisition with mean of 4.093, followed by finance (4.067) and housing construction (1.9067). ALHIKMAH Cooperative societies, the common activity is finance/loan with a mean of 4.220; followed by land acquisition and house construction with a mean of 1.366.

It is observable that KWASU has stronger participation in land acquisition and housing construction with higher mean values while Alhikmah cooperative societies has greater participation in finance/loan. At $p=0.000 < 0.005$, the null hypothesis is rejected; as the test statistics show that there are statistically significant differences between the activities of cooperative societies with regards to land activities, with Kwasu cooperatives showing higher levels of participation.

Supporting this, a recent study on cooperative societies in Edo State, Nigeria, highlighted the

significant contributions of these societies to housing delivery, emphasizing their role in providing housing loans and facilitating land acquisition and development (International Journal of Civil Engineering, Construction and Estate Management, 2023). These findings also align with other research, such as the study on the housing intervention strategies of cooperative societies, which identified land acquisition and provision of special loans for building and land title documents as the most effective strategies in meeting housing needs (International Journal of Community and Cooperative Studies, 2023). The consistency of these results across various contexts highlights the pivotal role of cooperative societies in land and housing activities, particularly in regions like KWASU where their participation is notably robust.

RELIABILITY TEST TO ASCERTAIN IF THE ITEM SCALE ARE SUITABLE FOR ACHIEVING OBJECTIVE 2

The reliability test was carried out on the 9 items scale for housing intervention strategies by five (5) officials across the five cooperative societies in the selected tertiary institution by using a 4-point scale as earlier adopted by Abdulkareem et. al., (2020) in their studies of effectiveness of housing intervention strategies. The study underscores the necessity for policymakers to consider

cooperative societies as vital players in housing development. By showcasing the success of housing interventions through cooperatives, it advocates for the formulation and implementation of policies that support and enhance the operations of cooperative societies in housing provision.

Nine items were selected arrived from literatures (See, Abdulkareem et. al., 2020) and also gotten from the official of cooperative societies. The table below shows the results of the reliability of the 9 items across the five selected tertiary institution cooperative society;

Table 4: Housing finance strategies on a 9-item scale using a 5-point relevant scale

S/N	Strategies of housing finance agreement	No in	I-CVI	Pc	Kappa
1.	Land acquisition, layout and allocation	5	1.000	0.03125	1.000
2.	Processing of building and land title doc.	5	1.000	0.03125	1.000
3.	Acquisition of building materials	5	1.000	0.03125	1.000
4.	Provision of general loans	5	1.000	0.03125	1.000
5.	Specific loan for land purchase	5	1.000	0.03125	1.000
6.	Provision of special loans for renovation of existing building	4	0.800	0.15625	0.7630
7.	Collective purchase of land and embarking on building construction	4	0.800	0.15625	0.7630
8.	Outright acquisition of complete housing	4	0.800	0.15625	0.7630
9.	Accessing housing loans from government Agencies/banks	4	0.800	0.15625	0.7630

This study has important implication which suggests that the data was gathered with great reliability. Cohen's Kappa establishes six levels of agreement: none (0–20), minimal (21-39), weak (40–59), moderate (60–79), strong (80–90), and almost perfect (above 90), according to McHugh (2012). It is used to assess the dependability of categorical data. The study's Table 3.6 shows that the 9-item scale's Kappa values range from moderate to nearly perfect agreement, with all values over 76%. This raises the credibility of the study's

findings and conclusions by indicating that the measures are consistently trustworthy (McHugh, 2012).

DISCUSSION OF RESULT

OBJECTIVE ONE: Current activities of cooperative societies across three levels (land acquisition, finance and construction) of the housing supply value chain

ANALYSIS TOOL: Descriptive statistics, using median frequencies of Likert scale items.

PROCEDURE: The median frequency count was used as a tool for analysis, as is appropriate for frequencies of Likert scale items.

Table 5 Extent of Participation of Cooperative Societies in housing finance

A-IHikmah CS					
Loan	25(61.0%)	10(24.4%)	2(2.9%)	2(2.9%)	2(2.9%)
Land acquisition	5(12.2%)	10(24.4%)	20(48.8%)	5(12.2%)	1(2.4%)
Construction	0(0%)	1(2.4%)	2(4.9%)	8(19.5%)	30(73.2%)
Al-Halal CS					
Loan	25(49.0%)	17(33.3%)	3(5.9%)	4(7.8%)	2(3.9%)
Land acquisition	26(51.0%)	16(31.4%)	5(9.8%)	2(3.9%)	2(3.9%)
Construction	0(0%)	1(2.0%)	5(9.8%)	10(19.6%)	35(68.6%)

Source: Field Survey (2024)

As shown in the table 4.3 the extent of participation of cooperative societies was carried out across all the 2 cooperative societies. Al-Hikmah CS loan activities take up 25(49.0%) while land acquisition is low 20(48.8%). Loan activities in Al-Halal cooperative society is 25(49.0%) and land

activities 30(60.0%). This implies that land acquisition activities is higher than both loan activities and construction activities in Kwasu CS. In Kwasu CS loan activities is higher than land acquisition with 38(76.0%) to 30(60.0%) while construction activities is very low with 0(0.0%).

ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH OBJECTIVE 2: STRATEGIES OF HOUSING FINANCE ACROSS THE STUDY AREA

Table 6: Ranking of Housing intervention strategies (AL-HIKMAH CS)

S/N	Housing intervention strategies (AL-HIKMAH)	Mean	Std-Deviation	Rank
1	Land acquisition, layout and allocation	2.76	1.220	4 th
2	Processing of building and land title document	2.73	1.205	5 th
3	Acquisition of building materials	4.05	1.161	1 st
4	Specific loan for land purchase	3.32	1.368	2 nd
5	Provision of special loans for renovation of existing building	2.83	1.093	3 rd
6	Collective purchase of land and embarking on building construction	2.32	0.934	6 th
7	Outright acquisition of complete housing	1.83	0.972	7 th
8	Accessing housing loans from government agencies/bank	1.46	0.897	8 th

Source: Field Survey (2024)

The table 6 shows the mean and standard deviation of the various strategies adopted by AL-HIKMAH cooperative societies with its corresponding ranking of mean score of each strategy. The strategies with the highest mean and ranked 1st are acquisition of building materials with a mean of 4.05 and standard deviation of 1.161 while specific loan for land purchase and provision of special loans for renovation of existing building ranked 2nd and 3rd with a mean of 3.32 and 2.83 respectively. The implication of this study is that ranking of the acquisition of building materials as the top strategy implies that members of AL-

HIKMAH cooperative societies prioritize immediate construction needs. This focus on tangible, immediate assets is crucial for enabling members to commence or complete building projects, thus addressing housing needs directly. This study is in line with the study of Abdulkareem et al. (2020) the authors noted the effectiveness of targeted financial interventions in housing provision. Their findings support the implication that specific loans, whether for land purchase or renovation, are essential strategies for cooperative societies aiming to enhance their members' housing conditions.

Table 7: Ranking of Housing intervention strategies (AL-HALAL CS)

S/N	Housing intervention strategies	Mean	Std-Deviation	Rank
1	Land acquisition, layout and allocation	4.43	0.728	1 st
2	Processing of building and land title document	3.71	1.205	4 th
3	Acquisition of building materials	4.25	0.845	2 nd
4	Specific loan for land purchase	3.96	0.937	3 rd
5	Provision of special loans for renovation of existing building	2.96	1.131	6 th
6	Collective purchase of land and embarking on building construction	3.16	1.286	5 th
7	Outright acquisition of complete housing	2.53	1.222	7 th
8	Accessing housing loans from government agencies/bank	1.67	0.816	8 th

Source: Field Survey (2024)

The table shows the various strategies in housing finance has adopted by AL-HALAL cooperative societies with its mean score and standard deviation of individual strategies. Land acquisition, layout and allocation ranked 1st with a mean of 4.43 and a corresponding value of standard deviation of 0.728, acquisition of building materials and specific loan for land purchase with a mean of 4.25 and

3.96 respectively and ranked 2nd and 3rd amongst the strategies of housing intervention. This study is in line with the study of Abdulkareem et al. (2020) the authors noted that land acquisition, acquisition of building materials and specific loans, whether for land purchase or renovation remains essential strategies for cooperative societies aiming to enhance their members' housing conditions.

ANALYSIS OF OBJECTIVE 3: TO EXAMINE THE STRATEGIES OF HOUSING FINANCE. IN THE STUDY AREA

Table 8: Descriptive (Frequency) of Cooperators Satisfaction with Cooperative Societies

Cooperative Societies	Attributes	Mean	Std-D	Rank
AL-HIKMAH	Interest rate	3.44	1.467	2 nd
	Affordability	2.88	1.536	5 th
	Transaction cost	3.44	1.501	3 rd
	Availability	3.07	1.555	4 th
	Collateral	4.56	0.896	1 st
AL-HALAL	Interest rate	3.78	1.604	3 rd
	Affordability	3.27	1.498	4 th
	Transaction cost	3.25	1.495	5 th
	Availability	3.88	1.409	2 nd
	Collateral	4.55	0.783	1 st

Source: Field Survey (2024)

The Table 9 above shows the cooperator level of satisfaction with cooperative societies (SC) in Al-Hikmah cooperative societies with collateral, interest rate and transaction cost ranked 1st, 2nd, and 3rd respectively with a mean of 4.56, 3.44 and 3.44. while in Al-Halal cooperative societies both ranked collateral, availability and interest rate 1st, 2nd and 3rd with a mean of 4.55 and 4.24, 3.88 and 3.98, 3.78 and 3.54 respectively.

This implies that different cooperative societies may have varying factors that significantly influence member satisfaction. For instance, in Al-Hikmah, the presence of collateral and the interest rate seem to be the primary determinants of satisfaction, while in Al-Halal, collateral and availability appear to be more crucial. Such findings could inform cooperative societies about the areas they need to focus on to enhance member satisfaction and retention. This is line with the findings of Abdulkareem et al. (2020).

Table 9: Cooperators Satisfaction Index (CSI) for CS

Attributes	Range of Dissatisfaction Index (RDI)		RDI(Buscom)	RDI(Al-Hikmah)		
	Mean	Std-D				
Interest rate	3.44	1.467	1.87	1.56		
Affordability	2.88	1.536	1.80	2.12		
Transaction cost	3.44	1.501	2.27	1.56		
Availability	3.07	1.555	1.72	1.93		
Collateral	4.56	0.896	0.73	0.44		
Average	3.478	1.391	1.678	1.522		
	Al-Hikmah CS and Al-Halal CS					
Interest rate	3.44	1.467	3.78	1.604	1.56	1.22
Affordability	2.88	1.536	3.27	1.498	2.12	1.73
Transaction cost	3.44	1.501	3.25	1.495	1.56	1.75
Availability	3.07	1.555	3.88	1.409	1.93	1.12
Collateral	4.56	.896	4.55	.783	0.44	0.45
Average	3.478	1.391	3.746	1.358	1.522	1.254

Source: Author's Computation

The Table 10 above shows that the CSI attributes for Al-Hikmah CS has an Average mean of 3.478, and the Range of dissatisfaction Index (RDI) of 1.522., the average range of dissatisfaction (ARD) where

the smallest is better (Sani, 2015), it can be observed that the ARD for Al-Hikmah cooperative have the smallest value of 1.522. The ARD of Al-Hikmah and Al-Halal is 1.522 and 1.254 respectively.

Al-Hikmah and At-Halal CS					
Interest rate	0.340	0.324	1.050	90	0.296
Affordability	0.390	0.318	1.225	90	0.224
Transaction cost	0.190	0.315	0.604	90	0.547
	0.810	0.310	2.612	90	0.011
Availability					
Collateral	0.010	0.175	0.057	90	0.955
Collateral	0.300	0.229	1.312	101	0.193

Source: Author's Computation from (2024)

A comparison of cooperators' satisfaction with house loan availability between Al-Hikmah Cooperative Society (CS) and Al-Halal Cooperative Society shows a significant outcome at the 0.05 level of significance (sig. value of 0.011<). This suggests that there is a statistically significant variation in cooperators' satisfaction levels with the availability of house financing between the two cooperative societies.

This research implies that Al-Hikmah CS and Al-Halal CS may have distinct approaches or offerings regarding home finance availability, resulting in variable degrees of satisfaction among their members. Further investigation might be performed to determine the exact variables contributing to this disparity and to suggest areas for improvement in either cooperative society.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The results showed that in Al-Hilal CS, land-related activities are more prevalent than loan-related and construction-related activities. It is clear that cooperative societies have aided employees in a variety of housing interventions, but there is still a need to reinforce the weaker areas of intervention, such as buying land collectively, buying a whole home outright, and getting a home loan from a bank or government agency. The National Housing Policy of Nigeria should be reviewed to incorporate cooperative societies into the policy for a combined effect. This will go a long way in saving public workers from the stress and pains of owning their own houses.

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